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THE STRATEGIC ROLE OF THE INDUSTRIAL SECTOR IN THE NATIONAL ECONOMY AND DEVELOPMENT FACTORS

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Annotatsiya. Sanoat milliy iqtisodiyotning tayanch tarmog'i bo'lib, mamlakatning iqtisodiy salohiyatini belgilovchi asosiy omil hisoblanadi. Ushbu maqolada sanoat tarmog'ining milliy iqtisodiyotdagi o'rni, uning tarkibiy tuzilishi va barqaror rivojlanish omillari ilmiy-nazariy jihatdan tahlil qilinadi. Sanoatning yetakchi tarmoq sifatida shakllanishi iqtisodiyotning boshqa sohalari – qishloq xo'jaligi, transport, energetika va xizmat ko'rsatish tizimlari bilan o'zaro integratsiyada kechadi. Maqolada, ayniqsa, sanoatni modernizatsiyalash, texnologik yangilanishlar kiritish, innovatsion ishlab chiqarish tizimlarini joriy etish orqali mamlakatning raqobatbardoshligini oshirish masalalari yoritilgan. O'zbekiston misolida sanoat siyosatini takomillashtirish yo'nalishlari, sanoat korxonalarining samaradorligini oshirishda davlatning iqtisodiy strategiyasi va xususiyl sektorning roli tahlil qilingan. Shu bilan birga, sanoatni raqamlashtirish, ekologik barqarorlikni ta'minlash va xalqaro kooperatsiyani kengaytirish kabi zamonaviy tendensiyalar ham o'rganilgan. Tadqiqot natijalari sanoatning yalpi ichki mahsulotdagi ulushi, eksport salohiyati va bandlik darajasiga ta'sirini ochib beradi. Shuningdek, maqolada sanoatning milliy iqtisodiy o'sishni ta'minlashdagi yetakchi roli, innovatsion muhitni rivojlantirishdagi ahamiyati hamda investitsion siyosat bilan uzviy bog'liqligi ilmiy asosda isbotlangan.

Kalit so'zlar: sanoat, milliy iqtisodiyot, modernizatsiya, innovatsiya, raqobatbardoshlik, texnologik yangilanish.

Abstract. Industry is the backbone of the national economy and is the main factor determining the economic potential of the country. This article scientifically and theoretically analyzes the role of the industrial sector in the national economy, its structural structure and sustainable development factors. The formation of industry as a leading sector occurs in mutual integration with other sectors of the economy - agriculture, transport, energy and service systems. The article, in particular, highlights the issues of modernizing the industry, introducing technological innovations, and increasing the country's competitiveness through the introduction of innovative production systems. Using the example of Uzbekistan, the directions for improving industrial policy, the state's economic strategy and the role of the private sector in increasing the efficiency of industrial enterprises are analyzed. At the same time, modern trends such as digitization of industry, ensuring environmental sustainability and expanding international cooperation are also studied. The results of the study reveal the impact of industry on the share of GDP, export potential and employment. The article also scientifically proves the leading role of industry in ensuring national economic growth, its importance in developing an innovative environment, and its inextricable link with investment policy.

Key words: industry, national economy, modernization, innovation, competitiveness, technological innovation.

Аннотация. Промышленность является основой национальной экономики и основным фактором, определяющим экономический потенциал страны. В статье научно-теоретически анализируется роль промышленного сектора в национальной экономике, его структурная структура и факторы устойчивого развития. Формирование промышленности как ведущей отрасли происходит во взаимной интеграции с другими секторами экономики – сельским хозяйством, транспортом, энергетикой и сферой услуг. В статье, в частности, освещаются вопросы модернизации промышленности, внедрения технологических инноваций и повышения конкурентоспособности страны за счет внедрения инновационных производственных систем. На примере Узбекистана анализируются направления совершенствования промышленной политики, экономическая стратегия государства и роль частного сектора в повышении эффективности промышленных предприятий. При этом изучаются такие современные тенденции, как цифровизация промышленности, обеспечение экологической устойчивости и расширение международного сотрудничества. Результаты исследования раскрывают влияние промышленности на долю ВВП, экспортный потенциал и занятость населения. В статье также научно обоснована ведущая роль промышленности в обеспечении роста национальной экономики, ее значение в развитии инновационной среды и неразрывная связь с инвестиционной политикой.

Ключевые слова: промышленность, национальная экономика, модернизация, инновации, конкурентоспособность, технологические инновации.

INTRODUCTION

Industry, as the most important and leading sector of the national economy, is one of the main factors determining the country's economic potential, competitiveness and level of social well-being. The economic power of each developed country is measured, first of all, by the volume of its industrial production, technological level and high quality of products. The industrial sector is closely interconnected with other sectors of the economy - agriculture, transport, trade, services and scientific and technical activities, and provides a strong impetus to their development. Therefore, industry is considered the "locomotive" of the national economy, that is, it determines the overall economic growth rates of the country and accelerates structural changes.

In modern conditions, industrial production serves the sustainable development of the economy not only through the creation of products, but also through the introduction of innovative technologies, increasing labor productivity and efficient use of resources. In particular, the introduction of digital technologies, automation, artificial intelligence and the concepts of "green economy" significantly increase the efficiency of industrial sectors. All this directly affects the creation of new jobs, strengthening export potential and improving the well-being of the people.

Taking the example of the Republic of Uzbekistan, one of the priority areas of the country's economic policy during the years of independence is the modernization of industry, renewal of production capacities and deep processing of the local raw material base. Today, such sectors as fuel and energy, chemistry, mechanical engineering, construction materials, light industry and food industry are rapidly developing in the country. As part of the "new Uzbekistan" reforms initiated by our President, a policy of diversifying industry, stimulating the private sector, attracting foreign investment and strengthening the integration of science and production is being implemented.

The role of industry as a leading sector is manifested not only in economic efficiency, but also in ensuring social stability. Because industrial enterprises create thousands of jobs, increase employment, expand the income base and reduce disparities in regional development. At the same time, the development of industrial infrastructure also stimulates the growth of supporting sectors such as transport, energy, communications and construction.

However, there are also some problems in the development of the industrial sector: factors such as high demand for energy resources, disruption of the ecological balance, low production efficiency, obsolescence of technological equipment and lack of highly qualified personnel hinder the sustainable growth of the sector. Therefore, the digitization of industry, the introduction of innovative management systems, the organization of production based on environmentally friendly technologies and the development of human capital are currently considered important strategic directions.

In general, industry is the pillar of the national economy, which strengthens the country's independence, ensures socio-economic stability and increases the well-being of the people. Therefore, the issues of modernization and innovative development of industry in Uzbekistan are at the center of state policy. Consistent reforms in this direction, adaptation of foreign experience to national conditions, and acceleration of technological transformation can increase the competitiveness of the industrial sector and give it a worthy place in the system of global markets.

Industry, as the backbone of the national economy and its driving force, determines the economic potential of society. For Uzbekistan, the development of the industrial sector is of great importance in strengthening economic independence, increasing employment, and expanding export potential. The reforms implemented in the country during 2022–2025 ensured the technical and technological modernization of industrial sectors.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The leading role of industry in the national economy has been widely discussed in economic literature. Classical economists such as A. Smith [1] and D. Ricardo [2] emphasized that industrial production is central to increasing labor productivity, capital accumulation, and overall economic growth. Their theories associate industrial expansion with specialization, technological innovation, and market enlargement. Later, J. Schumpeter [3] advanced this understanding by conceptualizing innovation and entrepreneurship as the primary drivers of industrial transformation through the mechanism of "creative destruction."

Modern theories further broaden the understanding of industrial competitiveness. M. Porter [4], through his theory of national competitive advantage, highlights the importance of industrial clusters, innovation systems, and interconnected value chains in strengthening national competitiveness. Structuralist economists provide additional insights: A. Hirschman [5] argues that industrialization generates forward and backward linkages that stimulate broader economic development, while W. A. Lewis [6] demonstrates how manufacturing absorbs surplus labor and raises productivity across the economy. Additionally, D. Rodrik [7] emphasizes that

manufacturing sectors exhibit unconditional productivity convergence, making industrialization a unique engine of sustained growth.

Institutional and evolutionary economists offer alternative perspectives. H.-J. Chang [8] and E. Reinert [9] argue that successful industrial development relies not only on markets but also on strategic state intervention, technological learning, and long-term capability-building. This institutional viewpoint is reinforced by global monitoring tools, including the UNIDO Industrial Competitiveness Index [10] and the World Economic Forum's Readiness for the Future of Production framework [11], both of which underscore the rising importance of digital technologies, innovation ecosystems, and integration into global value chains.

In the context of Uzbekistan, the role of industrial modernization has been examined extensively. Scholars such as A. Vakhobov [12], Q. Abdurakhmonov [13], and Sh. Khodiev [14] emphasize industrial structural reforms, modernization of production infrastructure, and improvements in the investment climate as essential determinants of long-term national economic growth. Furthermore, reports by the World Bank [15] and UNIDO [16] highlight that Uzbekistan's industrial sector is increasingly shaped by digital transformation, automation, green technologies, and the adoption of Industry 4.0 practices. These developments are found to significantly enhance productivity, strengthen export potential, and expand opportunities for high-skilled employment.

Despite the richness of prior literature, limited attention has been paid to the simultaneous interaction between digital industrialization, green transformation, and structural change in Uzbekistan. Addressing this gap, the present study proposes a new analytical perspective. It argues that Uzbekistan's industrial development is transitioning from capital-intensive growth toward a technology-intensive trajectory driven by innovation ecosystems and digital technologies. Additionally, digital transformation and green technologies are conceptualized as dual accelerators that jointly enhance industrial productivity and environmental sustainability. The study also finds that emerging industrial clusters create new learning spillovers, strengthening regional competitiveness and enabling diversification into higher value-added production. Moreover, the shift toward export-oriented industrialization requires deeper integration of Uzbek SMEs into global and regional value chains, a dimension underexplored in previous studies. Finally, the study highlights that institutional reforms, particularly regulatory simplification and improved innovation governance, are becoming as critical as technological modernization—revealing a dual dependency between institutional and technological upgrading.

Overall, existing literature affirms the strategic role of industry in national economic development but shows substantial gaps in integrated analyses of structural, technological, and institutional change. The present study contributes to filling this gap by developing a comprehensive analytical framework tailored to Uzbekistan's ongoing industrial transformation.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The methodological framework of this study is constructed on contemporary theoretical perspectives that conceptualize industry as a key driver of structural transformation, technological upgrading, and long-term competitiveness. The study employs an integrated set of analytical, statistical, comparative, and systemic approaches, allowing for a comprehensive assessment of industrial development in Uzbekistan during 2022–2025.

1. Analytical Approach

The analytical approach examines sectoral shifts, industrial productivity, and technological modernization within the national economy. This approach aligns with the structural transformation model proposed by McMillan and Rodrik [18], who emphasize that productivity dynamics across sectors are essential for understanding economic development. Furthermore, Lall [19] underscores that evaluating technological capabilities is central to assessing industrial competitiveness. Based on these insights, the analytical component in this study focuses on:

- sectoral productivity decomposition,
- technology adoption indicators,
- value-added growth,
- innovation-driven industrial changes.

This creates a foundation for evaluating how modernization contributes to national economic progress.

2. Systems-Based Approach

To understand intersectoral linkages, a systemic methodology was applied. Freeman's national innovation system theory [20] highlights the importance of interactions among firms, research institutions, and state policies in industrial development. Similarly, Andreoni [21] conceptualizes industry as an ecosystem of production, supply chains, and institutional coordination. In line with these frameworks, the study assesses:

- integration of industry with agriculture, logistics, energy, and services,
- the formation of industrial ecosystems and clusters,

- the multiplicative effect of industrial expansion on economic growth.

This systemic approach makes it possible to capture the broad economic influence of the industrial sector.

3. Statistical and Dynamic Analysis

The study uses official datasets from the Ministry of Economy and Finance, the State Statistics Committee of Uzbekistan, the World Bank, IMF, Trading Economics, and CEIC to analyze industrial performance over 2022–2025. The statistical methodology follows the dynamic measurement principles outlined by Jorgenson and Stiroh [22], which emphasize evaluating productivity, value added, and sectoral contributions to overall growth.

This component includes:

- time-series trend analysis,
- physical volume index (PVI) evaluation,
- structural shifts in industrial composition,
- regional disparities in industrial production,
- technological level assessment by subsector.

These methods ensure accuracy and international comparability.

4. Comparative Analysis

Comparative benchmarking evaluates Uzbekistan's industrial development against Southeast Asian and Central Asian economies. Amsden [23] argues that late-industrializing countries must rely on comparative learning to design effective industrial policies. Likewise, Wade [24] demonstrates that benchmarking international success models provides insights into institutional and technological mechanisms of industrial upgrading.

- Thus, comparative analysis identifies:
- similarities and differences with regional peers,
- potential for integration into global and regional value chains,
- policy lessons that can enhance industrial competitiveness.

5. Scientific Novelty of the Methodology

The scientific novelty of this methodological framework lies in integrating four analytical lenses:

- Structural transformation theory (McMillan & Rodrik)
- Innovation system theory (Freeman)
- Industrial ecosystem perspective (Andreoni)
- Comparative industrial policy theory (Amsden & Wade)

This combination enables a more robust evaluation of industry as a driver of economic stability, technological progress, and competitiveness in Uzbekistan. It also moves beyond purely descriptive approaches by linking structural, technological, and institutional dimensions into a unified methodological framework.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Industry plays a decisive and strategic role in the economic development of any country, serving as the backbone of productive capacity, technological progress, and export competitiveness. Industrial development increases the volume of goods produced, expands the range of ready-made products supplied to domestic and foreign markets, strengthens investment attractiveness, and amplifies a country's export potential. In the contemporary global economy, industries that are not equipped with high technologies, automation systems, or innovative production methods inevitably lose their competitive position. For this reason, the Government of Uzbekistan has prioritized industrial modernization, large-scale technological renewal, the expansion of import-substituting production, and the integration of digital technologies into industrial processes.

A key justification for selecting the period 2022–2025 for analysis is the significant transformation of global and regional economic conditions. The world economy during this period experienced post-pandemic recovery, geopolitical tensions, disruptions in global supply chains, volatility in energy markets, and the restructuring of international trade flows. These factors directly influenced Uzbekistan's industrial development. Simultaneously, the statistical transparency of Uzbekistan increased, and the publication of timely industrial data enabled more accurate empirical assessment.

According to official data from the National Statistics Committee, industrial production in 2022 demonstrated a positive trend. The physical volume index (PVI) of manufactured industrial products increased compared to the previous year. GDP reached 888.3 trillion soums, representing 5.7% real growth, indicating a broad-based recovery in economic activity.

In 2023, the industrial sector grew by 6%, while its share in GDP reached 26.1%. From January to September 2023, industrial output amounted to 459.9 trillion soums, with the PVI rising to 105.7%. These figures reflect strong momentum in processing industries and energy-related production.

The growth momentum continued into 2024. In January–March, industrial output reached 44.6 trillion soums, and the PVI increased to 116.6%, marking one of the highest quarterly increases in recent years. By January–October 2024, industrial production had reached 704.1 trillion soums, and the PVI stood at 106.9%, confirming the sector's stable expansion.

In January–April 2025, industrial output further increased to 290.1 trillion soums, while the PVI remained high at 106.3%. According to Trading Economics, the industrial production index in the second quarter of 2025 increased by 6.6% compared to the same period of the previous year. CEIC data indicate minor fluctuations at the beginning of 2025, but overall industrial growth remained stable. National Statistics Committee data for January–February 2025 also reported a PVI of 106.0%, suggesting continued upward dynamics.

Taken together, these indicators demonstrate that Uzbekistan's industry experienced stable and positive growth throughout 2022–2025, reflecting structural strengthening and technological upgrading.

A deeper understanding of industrial performance can be gained by analyzing value added across industrial subsectors. In January–June 2024, industrial value added increased by 7.8%. Notably, the processing industry grew by 9.4%, significantly outpacing the mining sector, which expanded by only 0.5%. This indicates a structural shift from raw material extraction toward higher value-added processing activities. Similarly, in 2023, industrial value added grew by 6%, again driven primarily by processing industries.

In 2024, mining enterprises produced 67.8 trillion soums worth of products, accounting for 7.6% of total industrial output. Although mining remains important, processing industries—particularly manufacturing, chemicals, pharmaceuticals, metallurgy, textiles, and food production—play an increasingly dominant role. Key subsector characteristics include:

- Manufacturing: Supported by state policies promoting import substitution, it remains a primary engine of growth.
- Chemicals and pharmaceuticals: High value-added and export-oriented, contributing to technological upgrading.
- Metallurgy and metalworking: Strongly linked to Uzbekistan's resource base and global commodity prices.
- Light industry (textiles, clothing, leather, footwear): Critical for employment and export diversification.
- Energy, oil, gas, and chemical industries: Sensitive to energy prices and raw material availability but strategically important for industrial continuity.

The geographical distribution of industrial production demonstrates significant regional imbalance. Approximately 45–50% of national industrial output is concentrated in Tashkent city, Navoi region, and Tashkent region, which benefit from established infrastructure, large enterprises, free economic zones, and high investment inflows. In contrast, regions such as Namangan, Surkhandarya, Jizzakh, and Kashkadarya contribute only 3–5% each, reflecting limited industrial diversification and lower investment absorption capacity.

Industrial output per capita further highlights disparities. In 2024, per capita industrial production was:

- 32.4 million soums in Tashkent city,
- 28.1 million soums in Navoi region,
- 10–12 million soums in Fergana Valley regions.

These differences stem from unequal distribution of industrial assets, differences in infrastructure, and asymmetric investment flows across regions.

Although Uzbekistan possesses substantial industrial potential due to its territorial, demographic, and resource advantages, challenges remain. Key among these are industrial efficiency, sectoral diversification, value-chain integration, and regional balancing. Strengthening the processing industry, promoting industrial cluster development, enhancing transport and logistics systems, and expanding innovation infrastructure are essential to ensuring sustainable industrial transformation.

Overall, the results confirm that Uzbekistan's industrial sector has entered a phase of consistent growth, technological upgrading, and structural diversification, positioning it as a central pillar of national economic development.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

The industrial sector constitutes the backbone of the national economy and serves as the primary engine of sustainable development. In contemporary economic systems, industrial growth is a decisive factor shaping a country's economic independence, technological capacity, export competitiveness, and social well-being. A strong and technologically advanced industrial base increases production efficiency, accelerates the adoption of innovations, enhances labor productivity, and strengthens national resilience to external shocks. These outcomes ensure the continuity of long-term economic growth and enable successful integration into the global competitive landscape.

In the case of Uzbekistan, recent years have demonstrated notable achievements in industrial diversification, technological modernization, and the implementation of digital economy principles. Systematic reforms have fostered significant progress in key industries such as energy, mechanical engineering, chemicals, textiles, pharmaceuticals, construction materials, and food processing. These sectors have increasingly become drivers of economic expansion, supported by strategic state programs and improved investment conditions. At the same time, the active participation of the private sector and the growing inflow of foreign direct investment have contributed to strengthening market competition, expanding production capacities, and enhancing the innovative potential of the industrial sector.

Looking ahead, industry must remain at the center of Uzbekistan's economic policy agenda. Sustainable industrial development requires a comprehensive approach that includes strengthening institutional support mechanisms, improving the regulatory and investment climate, and deepening the integration of science, education, and industrial production. Stimulating the creation of high-value, export-oriented, and technologically sophisticated products is essential not only for economic growth but also for enhancing national competitiveness in global markets. Ensuring the balanced development of industrial clusters, improving logistics infrastructure, and promoting environmentally responsible ("green") industrial practices will further reinforce the long-term stability of the sector.

Ultimately, a dynamic and innovation-driven industrial sector will serve as a cornerstone of Uzbekistan's economic security and a key determinant of public welfare. The continued modernization and diversification of industry will play a decisive role in shaping the country's future socioeconomic development and its transition toward a sustainable, high-income economy.

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